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The Influence of Social Media on the Voters Perception : An Empirical Study

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Abstract

The revolution in social media is rapidly changing the world and that includes elections too. US presidential election 2016 has been crowned as the “social media election” as it marks a turning point in political campaigning. This paper examines that Social media is going to play an important role in Indian politics. As per the analysis young generation spending maximum time on social media and they are the target segment for the political parties to make effective campaigning strategies on social media. One of the interesting outcomes of study was domination of social media on traditional media. The result indicates an alarming situation for traditional media. According to voters maximum traditional media like TV and news paper are highly influenced by political parties and not giving authentic information. Analysis also indicates that respondents are preferring social media due to cheapest & fastest way to express their ideas and reactions, a person can get detail information by videos and other ways by their own specific choices, on social media a person can share their own sentiments to others, it gives options to like, dislike, comments or shares the information to others, it is bilateral way of communication however traditional media is only one sided way of communication. The finding also indicates that adults believe that social media kills a lot of time. However young generation’s thoughts are not matching with adults voters. Majority of voters ranked first to the facebook and ranked second to whatsapp, while youtube and twitter ranked third and forth respectively. This study also reflects that facebook and whatsapp will be future campaigning tools for the political parties in Indian elections and going to play a major role in Indian politics. The study also reflects that majority of male & female voters like to “rational and entertaining” type of appeal in videos or other ways of messages on the sources of social media. Whereas young respondents are like to “entertaining and emotional” type of appeal in the videos and messages. However adult voters prefer “rational and entertaining” appeals in video and messages in the sources of social media.

Key Words: Social Media, Voters Perception, Indian Politics, Facebook, Whatsapp, Twitter, YouTube .

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